

PREVENTION OF UVR DEGRADATION ON POLYMER-BASED COMPOSITES BY NANO-ZNO & HGFS (INFILTRATION)

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Abstract

The harmfulness of ultraviolet radiation (UVR) to human bodies and polymer-based composites has recently been a concern in all research and engineering industries. As the usage of these composites has been massively increased, the protection of the human and the composites from UVR attack is certainly being a focus worldwide.

To protect the human bodies and the composites from the harmful UVR, nano-ZnO particles that possess intrinsic UV absorbability were introduced into polymer materials. Nano-ZnO filled epoxy-based smart memory polymers (EP-SMPs) and styrene-based smart memory polymers (S-SMPs) were developed to achieve their lower degree of UV degradation and maintain their moderate level of mechanical properties.

In this paper, an alternative is presented to fill nano-ZnO into hollow glass fibres (HGFs) and these fibres were embedded inside epoxy resin to form a UV-resistant composite. The function of HGF is to be a protective shell for the nano-ZnO particles from wearing away and dissolution out of the resin. Vacuum infiltration technique was used to fill nano-ZnO/epoxy into HGFs. In experiments, the composite with 4 wt.% nano-ZnO/epoxy filled into HGFs with their intervals of 0.2mm obtained the best UV absorbability. Because of the small inner diameter of HGF, the infiltration condition of nano-ZnO/epoxy was a concern for achieving a good UV absorbability and structural properties of the composite. This paper discusses the rheology behaviour and the characteristics of nano-ZnO/epoxy inside the HGF.

Keywords: Composite; Hollow glass fibre; ZnO/epoxy; Vacuum infiltration; Ultraviolet

1 Introduction

Ultraviolet radiation (UVR) is classified into three groups, UVA (315-400nm), UVB (280-315nm) and UVC (100-280nm). Theoretically, UVC (100-280nm) is almost totally absorbed by an ozone layer and only UVA and UVB reach the earth's surface. UVA has the highest intensity at 95% and the highest penetration power [1,6]. Its prolonged exposure has been a concern and its harmfulness has been proven in many researches which causes skin cancer and cataract in human bodies [2] and degrades polymer-based materials to decolourize, form cracks in polymer and delamination between fibres and matrix [3,7]. These defects cause the loss of mechanical properties of the materials such as impact strength. The loss is especially critical to the material being as structural component.

In the fact that more and more polymer composites are applied on structural constructions and exposing under UVR. Glass or carbon fibre reinforced polymer composites (GFRPCs or CFRPCs) are widely used in aircraft (A350 and B787), automobile (McLaren F1 and Lamborghini Sesto Elemento) and civil engineering industries because of their high design varieties, good strength-to-weight and stiffness-to-weight ratios and low maintenance cost due to their good corrosion and fatigue resistance. Such that the harmfulness of UVR on polymer materials is beginning a concern in engineering industry.

In this circumstance, composites should be designed with UV protect-ability for composite structural components, which would be exposed under the sunlight or space environment. Existing methods for protecting polymer composites from UV degradation include applying UV protective coating and embedding UV resistant fillers into polymers.

Nano-ZnO particles would be a good candidate which possess intrinsic UV absorbability, a full UVA and UVB absorption spectrum. There is an attempt to develop nano-ZnOs filled epoxy-based smart memory polymers (EP-SMPs) and polystyrene-based smart memory polymers (PS-SMPs) which results in achieving their lower degree of UV degradation and maintain their moderate level of mechanical properties [4]. An alternative method is developed by using HGF as a protection for nano-ZnOs from wearing away or dissolution out and embedded the filled fibres inside epoxy resin to form a UV-resistant composite. Vacuum infiltration technique is adopted to fill nano-ZnO/epoxy into HGFs. 4 wt.% nano-ZnO (100nm)/epoxy filled into HGFs with their intervals of 0.2mm was found to have the best UV absorbability [5]. To better understanding the phenomenon, rheology test of the matrixes and the observation of particle dispersion inside the HGF were conducted and will be presented in this paper.

2. Experimental Setup

Raw materials

Two types of nano-ZnOs, 20nm doped-ZnO and 100nm ZnO (undoped), used in this study are produced by American process and French process respectively. Their compositions, crystal structures and apparent (bulk) densities (0.532g/cm^3 and 0.560g/cm^3 respectively), which representing their deformability, are similar. They are both in nodular shape and in white colour. The surface area of 100nm ZnO is 31.42m^2 which is 25 times larger than 20nm doped-ZnO, which means 100nm ZnO has higher contact surface area with epoxy molecules inside the resin. 20nm ZnO is coated with a coupling agent (KH550) of Silane groups and the weight ratio is 99:1. The surfactant on 20nm ZnO is supposed to prevent the particle agglomeration and enhance the adaptability with epoxy resin which means strength the bonding of particle-resin molecule. No solvents were used in the dispersion processes.

HGF with outer diameter (OD) of $125\mu\text{m}$ and inner diameter (ID) of $100\mu\text{m}$ was produced by the Department of Aerospace Engineering of the University of Bristol. It has a static frictional coefficient of approximately 0.94 and density of 2.63g/cm^3 .

Araldite GY251 and hardener HY956 mixed in the weight ratio of 5:1 were to be the epoxy resin.

Samples preparations

In the rheology test, all fluid samples were mixed under room temperature and pressure. Different weight percentages of two types of ZnO, 2wt.%, 4wt.%, 5wt.% and 7wt.% were mixed with the epoxy undergoing mechanical stirring for 5mins and followed by sonication for 20mins, then added hardener and stirred for another 5mins. The fluid samples were produced at the same period of time and after mixing, they were kept at 0-3°C prior to the test.

Vacuum infiltration technique was adopted to infiltrate the matrixes into HGFs. Vacuum pump with the total ultimate vacuum pressure of 2Pa was applied for 10mins to ensure a full infiltration of each HGF with 100mm long. All specimen were cured under room temperature and pressure, 24 hours was needed for fully curing.

Rheology studies

The rheology studies of nano-ZnO/epoxy samples were conducted on rotational Rheometer (ARES#, TA Instruments) using a parallel plate geometry with 25mm diameter and 1mm gap. The effects of nano-ZnO's weight percentage, contact surface area and functionalization in epoxy resin on the fluid flow were evaluated by shear stress and viscosity changes along the shear rate from 0 to 250s⁻¹. The shear rate was in log scale for easy evaluation.

Infiltrant characteristics inside the HGF

The dispersion of 100nm ZnO particles inside epoxy resin and the degree of shrinkage of cured matrix inside HGF were observed by using optical microscope (OM).

3. Results and Discussions

Effects of ZnO content and functionalization on shear stress

Rheology flow of fluid determines the infiltration satisfaction. There are two major parameters to understand the rheology flow of fluid, shear stress and viscosity under shearing force. In the following, two sets of fluid samples according to shear stress and viscosity against shear rate are discussed. The two sets of fluid samples, shown in Figure 1 and 2, were 2wt.%, 4wt.%, 5wt.% and 7wt.% (yellow, red, blue and green respectively) of 100nm ZnO (solid line) and 20nm doped-ZnO (dashed line) mixed with epoxy resin. One neat epoxy resin (black solid line) was a control sample for reference purpose.

In Figure 1, yield stress is indicated as the starting shear at zero shear rate. It is the stress required to deform the microstructure of the fluid and simulate the flow of fluid. The amount of ZnO increases, the yield stress of the fluid increases. This indicated that particles interfered the bonding between polymer molecules, making the microstructure of resin with less mobility, resulted in the deformation difficulty. However, on the other hand, the particles could be regarded as a help in the stabilization of fluid flow.

4wt.% and 7wt.% 100nm ZnO/epoxy required much lower shear stress for deforming its microstructure and flowing along the shear rate compared with that of 20nm doped-ZnO/epoxy. The shear stress required to deform 2wt.% and 5wt.% of 100nm ZnO/epoxy and 20nm doped ZnO/epoxy behaved similar with little higher of 100nm ZnO/epoxy at low shear rate. Upon a certain shear rate, 2wt.% and 5wt.% 100nm ZnO/epoxy contrarily required lower shear stress. The coating might be destroyed by high shearing force and the molecules inside matrix became much complicated in shape and dispersion (inhomogeneous of matrix) resulting in much high shear stress was required to deform the microstructure of fluid. It is worth noting that the bond between the silane coating-ZnO particle is a hydrogen bond which is a kind of

secondary bond, so the bonding is weak and more susceptible to the applied shearing force. The results indicated that the coating on ZnO particle could not help in the fluid flow.

Figure 1. Shear stress against shear rate of different fluid samples

Effects of ZnO content and functionalization on viscosity

In Figure 2, 7wt.% 20nm doped-ZnO/epoxy was not accounted for the discussion due to its extremely high viscosity, which was around 46Pa.s along its plateau compared with other fluid samples. The results matched with the graph of shear stress against shear rate. The required shear stress to deform the microstructure of fluid could somewhat be relevant to the viscosity of fluid. Viscosity of fluid is the internal resistance force of molecules to inhibit the flow. Shear stress is the applied force acting on the microstructure of fluid and partly dependent on the viscosity of fluid.

Along the plateau, neat epoxy resin had a slightly increasing viscosity under the increasing shear rate, this phenomenon was also happened in the fluid samples of 20nm doped-ZnO/epoxy. This could be claimed that the coating enabled 20nm ZnO to behave similarly as the neat epoxy resin in terms of viscosity characteristic. The higher the weight percentages of ZnO, the deeper the increasing slope. After the critical viscosity, the

coating on ZnO might be destroyed by high shearing force and resulted in a complicated mixture (inhomogeneous) which led to an increase in the viscosity of fluid. Along the plateau, fluid samples of 100nm ZnO/epoxy had slightly decreasing viscosity. It should not be described as unstable of the undoped particles altering the epoxy resin, but they only adverse the behaviour of the base resin. The higher the weight percentages of ZnO, the deeper the decreasing slope. The ZnO would not be destroyed by the applied shearing force, instead the bonding between resin molecule-resin molecule and the bonding between particle-resin molecule were sheared further apart which resulted in lowering of the viscosity.

Every fluid sample had its initial viscosity and flowed slightly increasing or decreasing along its plateau until it reached a certain point of limit which was indicated as critical viscosity shown in the graph. After the critical viscosity, all fluid samples had a sudden drop of viscosity. 100nm ZnO/epoxy samples without coating dropped violently than 20nm doped-ZnO/epoxy samples. At this region, coating on ZnO particle could obviously show its stabilization effectiveness. It could help strengthening the bonding between particle-resin molecule, so a mild drop at the critical viscosity was resulted.

Figure 2. Shear viscosity against shear rate of different fluid samples

Generally, contact surface area with epoxy resin of 20nm doped-ZnO is 25 times lesser than that of 100nm ZnO and the bonding strength between particle-resin molecule of 20nm doped-ZnO is stronger than that of 100nm ZnO. It could be proved by the rheology results that a larger shear stress was required to deform the microstructure of fluid samples of 20nm doped-ZnO/epoxy with higher viscosity. ZnO particles is a metal oxide and can be defined as relatively undeformable. The epoxy resin is a thermoset polymer which their

polymer chains are in covalent bond and it is deformable under relatively high shearing force. So the bonding between particle-resin molecule would be the crucial factor to determine the rheology flow of fluid.

Conclusively, 4wt.% 100nm ZnO/epoxy had a gentle rheology flow and obtained the lowest shear stress and viscosity throughout the applied shear rate from 0 to 250s^{-1} among all the ZnO/epoxy fluid samples. And they were even lower than the neat epoxy resin after a certain point at low shear rate.

Dispersion of particles

After curing process, different weight percentages of 100nm ZnO in epoxy inside their individual HGF with inner diameter (ID) of $100\mu\text{m}$ were observed under optical microscope (OM) with 60x and 100x magnifications shown in Figure 3 and Figure 4 respectively. Particles dispersion and matrix shrinkage behaviour inside the HGF were investigated.

Neat epoxy was clear because no particles and bubbles were present. 5wt.% and 7wt.% ZnO/epoxy exhibited particle agglomeration. In 5wt.% ZnO/epoxy, white granules with size larger than 100nm were discovered, their size ranges from $1\mu\text{m}$ to $10\mu\text{m}$ could be easily found and their distribution was non-uniform. In 7wt.% ZnO/epoxy, the particle agglomeration was even severe. The white granules were densely packed inside the HGF and boundaries of granules were indistinctively observed.

In 2wt.% ZnO/epoxy, particle agglomeration was hardly found, instead, the particles were loosely dispersed and even distributed inside the HGF. It was observable that gap was present between particle-particle with uniform distance under this magnification. In 4wt.% ZnO/epoxy, agglomerated particles were hardly found but particles dispersed compactly which maximize the amount of ZnO particles with no agglomeration occurred to proceed their intrinsic UV absorbability.

Figure 3. Neat epoxy (upper left), 2wt.% ZnO (100nm)/epoxy (upper middle), 4wt.% ZnO (100nm)/epoxy (upper right), 5wt.% ZnO(100nm)/epoxy (bottom left) and 7wt.% ZnO (100nm)/epoxy (bottom right)

Shrinkage behaviour of resin

Apart from the ZnO particle agglomeration inside epoxy resin, different degrees of shrinkage were observed at the end of matrixes. Shrinkage of resin also leads to the particle agglomeration so it also affects the UV absorbability and mechanical properties of the composite. Epoxies are kinds of thermoset plastics which are always regarded as relatively low shrinkage and have been widely used as structural materials combining different reinforcements. However, when matrix is filled inside the micro-HGF, the shrinkage is more severe and is a crucial concern.

In Figure 4, higher shrinkage happened in neat epoxy resin without particles while lower shrinkage appeared in 5wt.% ZnO/epoxy where particle agglomeration occurred. It could be concluded that particle helps to stabilize the resin for obtaining a low degree of shrinkage.

Stabilization is important for most of the static and dynamic systems. For particles/matrix infiltration inside HGF, stabilization of particles is the even distribution of particles without agglomeration during infiltration and curing process. This would be the problem of force equilibrium exerted on each particle, the electrostatic force balanced between particle-particle and the bonding between particle-resin molecule.

Figure 4. Neat epoxy (left) and 5wt.% ZnO (100nm)/epoxy (right)

The symmetric diagram in Figure 5 shows the behaviour of matrix from being infiltrated to cured. During the vacuum infiltration process, applied force led the fluid to flow along the HGF, however, frictional force on the inner surface of HGF was exerted on the fluid and inhibit the fluid flow along two sides, so the fluid is in convex shape and moving forwards because the applied force at the centre is greater than the frictional force along two sides. During curing, the matrix shrank and after cured, a concave shape was obtained. The curvature is more obvious in resin without particles and when the inner diameter of HGF is small. So 4wt.% ZnO/epoxy having densely compacted and evenly dispersed particles would help to lower the degree of shrinkage of the matrix which maximize the amount of ZnO particles inside the HGF with no agglomeration occurred to proceed their intrinsic UV absorbability.

Figure 5. Schematic diagram showing the shrinkage of the neat epoxy resin and 5wt.% ZnO/epoxy matrix during curing process

4. References

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5. Conclusions

The influences of nano-ZnO's weight percentage, contact surface area and functionalization in epoxy resin on the fluid flow were evaluated by their shear stress and viscosity changes along the applied shear rate and the particles dispersion during curing and the degree of shrinkage after cured were examined using optical microscope. The following could be highlighted from the study.

1. 4wt.% 100nm ZnO/epoxy required the lowest shear stress to deform its microstructure and affected by the least viscosity to flow under the applied shear rate. 100nm ZnO without coating could effectively help in the rheology flow of fluid. The coating in 20nm ZnO could not show any effectiveness for the rheology flow of fluid.
2. The contact surface area of ZnO and the bonding strength of ZnO to epoxy resin would be the major factors to achieve a good rheology flow of fluid.
3. 5wt.% 100nm ZnO/epoxy with particle agglomeration had a lower degree of shrinkage compared with the neat epoxy resin. Noted that the shrinkage of resin would induce the nanoparticle agglomeration and at the same time nanoparticles could mitigate the shrinkage. A good proportion of nano-ZnO particles to epoxy resin molecules must be obtained to prevent the resin shrinkage and the particle agglomeration.
4. After cured, 4wt.% 100nm ZnO particles in epoxy resin could obtain an even and dense particle dispersion inside the HGF. It is believed that the applied shear stress could separate the bonding between particle-particle and the amount of particles could help lowering the resin shrinkage without occurring the particle agglomeration.
5. It is believed that the weight ratio of 100nm ZnOs:epoxy molecules=1:24 would be the best proportion for obtaining an optimal infiltration condition of smooth fluid flow with even and dense particle dispersion.

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